

ICHA 2025. Scientific Highlights

Fig. 1. Shauna Murray (Sydney, Australia) accepted to lead the big task of collecting information from Chairs and other participants and summarizing it in the Conference Highlights presented here.

The 21st International Conference on Harmful Algae (ICHA 2025) in Punta Arenas, Chile, provided an ideal showcase for novel insights in HAB research, some of which were driven by the increasingly novel application of key technologies (Fig. 1). On the local and regional scale, HABs are increasingly better understood through integrated technology as varied as remote- and in situ sensing observations (e.g., combining Imaging FlowCytobot (IFCB)/Planktoscope and satellite systems), and molecular approaches, including qPCR, metabarcoding and 'omics-based data on gene expression related to metabolic and toxic processes. Methods described at the conference included advanced mass spectrometry (e.g., LC-MS/MS), various biosensors (e.g., fish-gill assay, neuroreceptor binding assays (RBA), and the inclusion of classic environmental water quality, nutrient, and physico-chemical information for modelling. Long-term modelled data are derived and analysed locally but archived in regional and global databases because they may differ substantially between regions.

A further trend is the involvement of more people in HAB science, particularly citizen scientists, shellfish farmers and indigenous communities who assist with data collection, highlighted in

the inspiring plenary talk from **Manu Prakash** and multiple other presentations. Some projects used low-cost data-collection tools; others used this approach combined with high-technology tools such as biosensors, eDNA analyses, and passive samplers. HABs can have significant harmful impacts on coastal communities, justifying their classification as “natural disasters”. Overall, there was a clear emphasis on integrated, interdisciplinary approaches that merge ecological and oceanographic science with technological and socio-economic perspectives for effective HAB management and eventual control.

This conference, attended by 345 participants from 46 countries, also showcased increased development of HAB control and mitigation technologies, and once again highlighted the strong influence of climate change on every aspect of our oceans. It also showed that major HABs in new areas can still surprise us, and that there is much to learn about HAB species and their toxins, even for well-studied species and systems.

Ecology

In the ecology sessions, many studies emphasized the use of integrated laboratory experimentation and field sampling, sometimes in a novel way, to understand the physiological and life cycle drivers of field assemblages.

This included insights into the timing and relative importance of sexual and asexual reproduction of HAB species in the field (**Serena Sung-Clarke**), including drivers of cyst germination and its impacts on population growth and diversity (**Michael Brosnahan**). Analysis of how long-term monitoring data contribute to characterizing ecological niches revealed that microscopy and metabarcoding require an integrated approach (**Keelan Lawlor**). The macro- and micro-nutrient requirements of HAB taxa and new nutrient sources were investigated (**Patricia Glibert**). In the new methods session, the study of mucilage production contributed to a better understanding of the physiological and ecological functions of benthic dinoflagellates and highlighted the relevance of basal metabolites and TEPs in their biofilm dynamics (**Nadia Valeria Herrera**).

Oceanographic drivers were examined in terms of niches of HAB species (**Catharina Alves de Sousa**). Examples included El Niño and La Niña weather systems, upwelling, upwelling relaxation, stratification, freshwater influx, advection, and seasonality. Localities investigated included California (**Ruiz de la Torre**), the Baltic (**Bengt Karlson**), south-eastern Australia (**Dora Vig**), the Pacific Arctic (**Donald Anderson**), the Iberian Peninsula (**Eva Fonfria**) and southern Chile, including a notable plenary summary on Chilean HABs by **Benjamin Suárez** (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Different kinds of vessels, a small one for mussel aquaculture operations (left) and larger boats for artisanal fisheries, in Estero (Sound) de Castro. Castro city (42°28'S, 73°48'W), founded in 1527, is famous for its wooden stilt houses (palafitos). This town is the capital of Chiloé (Los Lagos Region, Chile), the island site of the world's second largest production of mussels (photo Benjamin Suárez).

Fig. 3. The Ecology, Biology, and Biogeography session, chaired by Ian Jenkinson (left to right, 1st left) and Máximo Frangópulos (last, right) with presentations from Jorge Mardones, Patricia Glibert, Catharina Alves-de-Souza and Chris Gobler (2nd to 5th)

The role of HABs in producing favourable or unfavourable water conditions was also examined, such as causing nocturnal oxygen collapse in some mixotrophic systems (**Christopher Gobler**). New sources of nutrients for HABs were discussed, such as off the West Florida Shelf, where so-called “blue holes” are active N-processing hotspots exporting reduced N (notably NH_4^+), facilitating *Karenia brevis* blooms (**Patricia Glibert**). Dense blooms of *Alexandrium ostenfeldii* utilize DON as an N source, while its allelopathic activity toward co-occurring phytoplankton species facilitates N uptake (**Elin Lindehoff**). A critical view on methodologies for nutrient analysis was also discussed (**Wayne Litaker**). Several talks examined the role of microplastic particles from buoys and ropes in suppressing the growth of HAB species or contributing to HAB toxicity (**Jorge Mardones**). Improved strategies for real-time tracking of blooms were presented, focused on *Karenia brevis* and other bloom forming species in Florida (**Katherine Hubbard**). A plenary talk reviewing the role of GEOHAB in stimulating HAB research internationally over many years was given by **Elisa Berdalet**, who brought with her a suitcase of decades of hardcopy IOC-UNESCO reports. The value (and challenges) of the global long time series database HAEDAT was also presented (**Dave Clarke**; Fig. 3).

Cyanobacteria and Freshwater HABs

The cyanobacterial research sessions highlighted the roles of genetic and digital technologies in cyanoHAB detection and research, including molecular tools (**Mark Van Asten**) and digital holography (**Madison Bennett, Aditya Nayak**), and demonstrated that this area of research has come of age over the past 25 years (plenary by **Sandra Azevedo**). A high-resolution 3D imaging approach revealed how nutrients and temperature impact morphology in *Microcystis* spp. (**Ronojoy Hem**). A vast variation of cyanobacterial traits related to nutrient acquisition, photophysiology, and thermal performance across

species and genotypes was shown (**Arnaud Louchart, Carol Waldman**); even within genotypes, cyanobacteria can be highly variable, just like eukaryotic taxa (**Dedmer Van de Waal**), and high ecotype diversity of *Microcystis* adapted to local environmental conditions (**Gabriela Martínez**). The role of micronutrients such as iron in limiting and regulating cyanobacteria and their toxins was also examined (**Charlie Trick, Irena Creed**). A sustainable and innovative management system for toxic cyanobacteria blooms combining preventive strategies and the use of waste cyanobacteria as fertilizers was presented (**Maria G. Antoniou**). Cyanotoxins gained increased attention as a seafood safety concern this year, with new findings such as the first confirmed detection of saxitoxin production in Synechococcales (**Flavio Luis de Oliveira**), and the novel application of LC-HRMS for non-targeted analysis of cyanobacterial biotoxins (**Pearse McCarron**).

Taxonomy and Phylogeny

At the session on Taxonomy and Phylogeny, historical name changes were revisited, with a notable contribution by **Urban Tillmann** concerning the ichthyotoxic haptophyte *Prymnesium parvum*. Phylogenetic relationships within the marine euglenoids belonging to *Eutreptiella* suggested separation into several species (**Sinuhé Hernández Márquez**). Intracellular ultrastructure of the toxigenic and non-toxigenic

Fig. 4. Chairs and oral speakers of the Taxonomy and Phylogeny session. From left to right, Mitsunori Iwataki, Koyo Kuwata, Urban Tillmann, Catarina Churro, Yolanda Pazos (Chair), Liza Campbell (Chair) and Sinuhé Hernández Márquez.

Fig. 5. Ciguatera and Benthic HABs session chaired by Sam Murray and Catharina Alves-de-Souza (in the middle) with contributions from Amna Ashfaq, Jorge Diogéne, Taiana Darius (first three on the left), Silvia Nascimento and Chiara Melchiorre (last two on the right).

strains of *Azadinium* and *Amphidoma* were compared to identify structures associated with toxin production and the potential for morphological differentiation (**Koyo Kuwata**). Eleven species of the Amphidomataceae, including four newly recorded in the Northwest Pacific and three newly described species, were reported from Japan (**Mitsunori Iwataki**). The IOC-FAO IPHAB Task Team on Taxonomy also presented recent updates of the IOC/UNESCO Taxonomic Reference List of Harmful Algae (**Catarina Churro**; Fig. 4)

Toxicity and Toxicology Research Chemistry and toxins were once again a key theme, from advanced LC–HRMS workflows (**Elizabeth Mudge**), and LC–MS method innovation designed to monitor multiple classes of toxins (**Chiara Melchiorre**), through to continued advances in biosensors (**Jaume Reverté**) for rapid detection of concomitant toxins or the mechanisms of action of cyclic imines (**Jordi Molgó**). Isolation of polyketide toxins from free-living and symbiotic Symbiodiniaceae was reported (**Emily Jolly**). Results from Chile’s national monitoring programme revealed high levels of YTX and PTX in mussels from Chilean fjords (**Fernanda Barrera**), along with striking spiroside diversity in *Alexandrium ostentfeldii* from the Beagle Channel (**Luis Norambuena**). Collectively, these findings remind us that even after decades of research the toxin field continues to evolve.

Toxicological impacts on filter-feeding mollusks, farmed fish, and zooplankton were a focus of several presentations. Species of *Alexandrium* can cause a reduction in filtration rates in juvenile *Magallana gigas*, affecting their feeding rate and survival (**Ismavy Castillo**). Other harmful taxa, such as *Pseudochattonella cf. verruculosa*, *Thalassiosira pseudonana*, and *Heterosigma akashiwo*, have effects on farmed salmonid species, confirming that ROS-mediated oxidative stress is the main cause of pathologies (**Diego Caro**). Azithromycin (AZT) concentrations can enhance the impacts of toxic cyanobacteria on zooplankton, reflected in fundamental aspects of populations (**Michael Celano**).

Ciguatera poisoning (CP) remained a key focus, reflecting its continued global relevance and growing impact to non-endemic regions. This included recent progress in ciguatoxin chemistry (**Sam Murray**), the discovery of novel compounds, improved extraction and quantification techniques (**Melanie Roue**, presented by **Taiana Darius**), and the identification of new *Gambierdiscus* species (**Christopher Bolch**). In her Yasumoto award opening keynote, **Mireille Chinain** emphasised the value of combining traditional and “Western”-type knowledge in understanding and managing CP; knowledge that includes natural plant-based remedies, awareness of high-risk fishing areas, and recognition of toxic fish by indigenous communities. Outreach activities linking science with local practices were

showcased as an effective way to reduce CP cases. In Brazil, a collaborative effort combining toxin analysis, species identification, and community education has already led to measurable declines in reported poisonings (**Silvia Nascimento**) (Fig. 5)

A remote plenary presentation from **Aifeng Li** highlighted the key importance of genomic, transcriptomic, toxin and laboratory culture experiments in elucidating the genetic basis of BMAA (β -N -methylamino-L-alanine) synthesis in diatoms.

Ichthyotoxic HABs

Presentations on ichthyotoxic HABs dealt with functional interactions of ichthyotoxic species in plankton communities and the (“toxic”) mechanisms of collateral damage to fish and other marine fauna. By combining metabolomic and metagenomic approaches linked by gene expression to functional bioassays, it has been possible to develop and apply functional models of toxicity of groups of putative ichthyotoxins, and to use them as templates to explore potency and mechanisms of new ichthyotoxins. For example, among the known polyether ichthyotoxins, the sterolysins—originally only dinoflagellate karlotoxins (KmTx) but also including amphidinols (AM) and more recently haptophyte leadbeaterins (LBT) among others—provide a rich palette for integrative studies on biosynthesis and regulation by polyketide synthases (PKS), and for exploring their membrane-disruptive effects on fish gills and plankton predators and competitors (**Anita Solhaug**). In a compelling keynote from **Bernd Krock**, the re-emergence of *Chrysochromulina leadbeateri* in spring 2025 as a major fish-killing bloom taxon was definitively linked to leadbeaterin-1 (LBT-1), and more broadly to sterolysin diversity during fish-killing *C. leadbeateri* blooms in northern Norway (**Ingunn Samdal**). Rapid advances have also been made in elucidating biosynthetic pathways for PKS-based sterolysins and their eco-evolutionary origins among haptophytes and dinoflagellates (**Chris Miles**). These pioneering studies presented at ICHA25 are expected to deepen our understanding of global fish-mortality events associated with HABs, such as those involving *Fibrocapsa ja-*

Fig. 6. Participants in a session on Ichthyotoxic HAB mechanisms and biological interactions. Front row (left to right): Lixia Shang, Jiyeon Sung, and Shauna Murray; back, Raph Kudela, and session chairs Thomas Larsen and Kristoff Möller (photo ICHA 2025 LOC).

ponica (Raphidophyceae) from Argentina (**Delfina Aguiar Juárez**) and a HAB in a Northern Tunisian Lagoon (**Afef Fathalli**). An ocean-rheology working group described how polymeric secretions of some HAB species could play a role in killing fish and other organisms through rheotoxicity (**Ian Jenkinson**) (Fig. 6)

Novel insights into the fish-killing mechanisms of harmful algal blooms (HABs) at the HAB organism level were provided from multifaceted and comparative perspectives (**Lixia Shang**). A fundamental mechanism regulating growth and toxigenicity of *Margalefidinium polykrikoides* is physical dynamics driven by turbulence (**Jiyeon Sung**). Successful integration of remote-sensing imaging with classical eco-physiological laboratory studies helped define the ecological footprint, impacts, and dispersion of *Heterosigma akashiwo* blooms in San Francisco Bay, CA, USA (**Raphael Kudela**).

A novel report of an unprecedented large-scale bloom of a *Karenia cristata* in South Australia (now in its eighth month and ongoing) was associated with extensive deaths of marine life and human respiratory irritation (**Shauna Murray**). Isolates of this species were confirmed to produce brevetoxins (BTX) in culture at levels similar or higher than *Karenia brevis*. Because this taxon originally described from the South African coast has never been associated with harmful algal events in

Australia, its origin and potential recurrence remain unknown.

HAB Mitigation and Control

The number of presentations on mitigation and control measures at this ICHA conference continued to increase relative to previous ICHAs. These were comprehensively reviewed in this session (**Vera Trainer**). Modified clays have been shown to efficiently remove *K. brevis* in some studies, and have also been applied to several HAB species in China (**Zhiming Yu, Xiuxian Song**) and in Chilean, Scottish and Norwegian waters (**Ana Flores Leñero**). Some modified-clay approaches have also been shown to degrade toxins, including a study that found over 90% degradation of PSTs from *Alexandrium pacificum* and *Karenia brevis* into lower-toxicity products (**Lianbao Chi**).

HAB Forecasting and modelling

New forecasting approaches using oceanographic data collection, including data refined using machine-learning and fuzzy logic, were shown to improve predictive ability across multiple systems. The use of passive samplers, such as SPATT bags (**Máximo Jorge Frangópulos Rivera, Christopher Miles, Ingunn Samdal**) to collect toxins, as well as other forms of passive samplers for Edna, was introduced, including the involvement of local communities and citizen scientists. Research in New Zealand and North

America showed such community involvement could enhance data collection on HABs and their impacts. New HAB-monitoring systems have been implemented in Mexico, Chile, Colombia, the Baltic Sea, and other regions, and some of these have allowed predictions up to 30 days before toxins appear (**Leonardo Guzmán**; Fig. 7)

HABs and climate change

This conference documented the overwhelming influence of climate change on HABs worldwide. This includes changes in the timing of HAB initiation and termination, in nutrient sources and inputs, and in HAB species distributions. These changes are often complex and region-specific – intensifying blooms in some regions, such as the North Sea (**Andrea Budisa**), becoming persistent such as *Gambierdiscus* populations in the Mediterranean Sea (**Jorge Diogène**), or leading to reduced phytoplankton abundance in other regions, such as areas around New Zealand. These changes are triggered by many different aspects of climate change, including extreme weather events –such as an extreme flood which appeared to trigger a bloom of *Dinophysis acuminata* in Brazil (**Luiz Mafra**) –freshening of waters, acidification and warming waters. While many of these changes are detrimental, some may reduce HAB events regionally, as conditions may become too warm for certain taxa. Climate change will make the co-occurrence of HABs and acidification more common as CO₂ levels continue to increase.

Extended bloom windows were seen in the Red Sea off the coast of Saudi Arabia, a region generally considered oligotrophic (**Afrah Al Othman**). Climate-linked changes in cyst germination phenology have been observed in *Alexandrium catenella* in the Gulf of Maine, with temperature-driven dormancy cycling producing maximum germination rates during spring (**David Ralston**). Warming trends in coastal waters may allow cysts to germinate earlier in the year, but germination rates remain in winter and early spring, resulting in little change to annual germling-flux patterns. Earlier initiation and longer inshore activity make retentive embayments key sentinels for HAB events. In the Pacific Arctic, a massive and persistent *A. catenella* cyst bed—many times

on turbulence and temperature, showing that *K. brevis* prefers warmer conditions and that storms may disrupt blooms. Climate-change-driven salinity changes have also affected HABs: freshening of northern basins appears to have led Baltic *Nodularia spumigena* strains towards long-term low salinity adaptation (**Carolyn Peter**).

HABs and Social Dimensions

Several presenters focused on societal aspects of HAB research (e.g. the UN Plankton Manifesto), including what can be learnt from them (**Gustaaf Hallegraeff**). Continuing education, especially with children in rural and urban areas in Chile, highlighted community knowledge, perceptions and responses to HABs (**Pamela Carbonell**). Interviews with tourists in the intermountain region of Utah (USA) has made it possi-

ble to understand and identify the level of knowledge about HABs, offering recommendations for public institutions to develop future educational campaigns (**Hannah Bonner**). In order to understand these multifactorial processes, it is important to incorporate new tools that allow communities to more accurately understand the data that affects the local economy in the event of a HAB (**Yingze Xu**). Finally, with a vision that encompasses eleven countries in Latin America and the Caribbean, the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) and the regional network REMARCO examined the current state of public policies in order to produce a regional reference document to guide and strengthen the development of national policies, thereby improving surveillance, early warning, and governance in these countries (**León Vergara**).

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